

OCEAN ICE News – February 2026

OCEAN ICE is a Horizon Europe project, funded by the European Commission and UKRI. OCEAN ICE stands for Ocean-Cryosphere Exchanges in Antarctica: Impacts on Climate and the Earth System.

OCEAN ICE News is a monthly newsletter updating about the project's progress, results, and other exciting events! Be sure to follow us on LinkedIn to stay informed.

Welcome!

Welcome to February's edition of OCEAN ICE News. We're excited to bring you the latest updates from the OCEAN ICE community.

In this issue, you'll meet our featured researcher of the month and catch up on key activities, such as an OCEAN ICE publication, OCEAN ICE at TRICUSO and PROS4SORP Webinar series, an article on Antarctic Icebergs getting Stuck on the Seabed and highlighting January's Climate Coffee. We have some upcoming Climate Coffee's that you can register for in February, March and April. Don't forget to mark your calendars for the upcoming events where OCEAN ICE will be represented.

We hope you enjoy exploring this month's updates, and we look forward to sharing more in March!

Researcher in the Spotlight: Antonio Novellino

Check out our latest 'Researcher in the Spotlight' feature on Antonio Novellino, a Research Manager at ETT, and WP7 Lead on Data Management for OCEAN ICE.

Read the feature on Antonio [here](#).

Stay tuned for more features from our Research Team in OCEAN ICE.

Catching up on the Latest OCEAN ICE Activities

OCEAN ICE at TRICUSO and PROS4SORP Webinar series

Andrew Meijers presented the white paper that has emerged from the September OCEAN ICE/SOOS workshop on ice covered oceans at both the TRICUSO annual scientific meeting and the PROS4SORP international seminar series. The TRICUSO meeting was in Bergen, 13-15th January, and on 20th January Andrew gave an expanded version of this talk as part of the Presenting Recent Ocean Science for the Southern Ocean Regional Panel (PROS4SORP) webinar series.

Read the full article [here](#).

Ocean-Cryosphere Exchange in Antarctica: Impacts on Climate and the Earth System

Looking forward: Community science priorities and strategies in the Southern Ocean for the InSync and IPY era

Andrew Meijers – British Antarctic Survey

Disclaimer: Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the authors only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Research Executive Agency (REA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

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OCEAN ICE Publication: Swirls and scoops: Ice base melt revealed by multibeam imagery of an Antarctic ice shelf

The autonomous underwater vehicle, *Ran*, was programmed to dive into the cavity of Dotson ice shelf, West Antarctica, and scan the ice above it with an advanced sonar. For 27 days, the submarine travelled a total of over 1,000 kilometres back and forth under the glacier, reaching 17 kilometres into the cavity. An ice shelf is a mass of glacial ice, fed from land by tributary glaciers, that floats in the sea above an ice shelf cavity. We have previously used satellite data and ice cores to observe how ice shelves change over time. By navigating the submersible into the cavity, we were able to get high resolution maps of the ice underside. In *Science Advances* the researchers report on the findings of this unique survey. Some things are as expected: The glacier melts faster where strong underwater currents erode its base. Using the submersible, scientists were able to measure the currents below the glacier for the first time and prove why the western part of Dotson Ice Shelf melts so fast. They also see evidence of very high melt at vertical fractures that extend through the glacier.

Read the full article [here](#).

OCEAN ICE Article on: When Antarctic Icebergs get Stuck on the Seabed: Why it Matters for Climate

Anna Olivé Abelló wrote an article for the IGE website: Antarctic icebergs are huge ice blocks that break off from glaciers and floating ice shelves and drift through the Southern Ocean. As these icebergs melt and release freshwater, they modify the global ocean circulation and therefore the global climate.

Icebergs also transport sediments and nutrients that fertilise the Southern Ocean, support phytoplankton growth, and indirectly help remove carbon dioxide locally from the atmosphere, playing thus an essential role in Earth's climate. Because of these multiple roles, icebergs need to be represented in numerical climate models to accurately simulate the ocean evolution and environmental conditions in a changing climate.

Read the full article here: [When Antarctic icebergs get stuck on the \(...\) | IGE Géosciences Environnement](#)

OCEAN ICE Climate coffee – January

Climate Coffee with Fehmi Dilmahamod on Characteristics of Mesoscale to Submesoscale Eddies in the Labrador Sea.

Characterization of coherent eddies is often based on gridded satellite altimetry products. In subpolar regions, these products face limitations due to their low spatial resolution and the decreasing Rossby radius of deformation at higher latitudes, making in situ observations indispensable for eddy characterization. Here, we present a census of mesoscale-to-submesoscale eddy characteristics in the Labrador Sea—a region where eddies play an important role in winter deep convection and subsequent restratification. Using ship-based observations, we fit an idealized eddy solution to horizontal velocity measurements acquired along ship tracks, determining an optimal eddy center and other key eddy properties. Based on three research cruises, we reconstructed 40 eddies ranging from 3 to 39 km in radius (mean 15 km) and azimuthal velocity

between 7 and 58 cm s⁻¹ (mean 26 cm s⁻¹). The azimuthal velocity structure implies, to a large extent, solid-body rotation in the eddy's inner core, while opposite signs of vorticity in the outer ring suggest strong vorticity shields. When compared to ship-based observations, the eddy field representation in gridded altimetry products is significantly distorted, with many eddies being underrepresented or undetected. This is even the case for larger-scale features despite having an eddy signature in the long-track altimetry product, which appears to be suppressed in the subsequent mapping methodology. Finally, comparisons with submesoscale-permitting numerical simulation output show favourable agreement, giving confidence in both the ship-based reconstruction and the numerical model's realism in representing high-latitude eddy dynamics.

29 January 2026 | 10:00 - 10:45 CET
Online

Fehmi Dilmahamod (GEOMAR)
Characteristics of Mesoscale-to-Submesoscale Eddies in the Labrador Sea: Insights from Ship Observations

Danish Meteorological Institute

ECRA

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Climate Coffees

Since its relaunch, the [Climate Coffee series](#) has been in full swing. If you've missed any of the recent ones, don't you worry, you may catch up [here](#).

Climate Coffee

OCEAN ICE Deliverables and Milestones submitted

The OCEAN ICE community has been busy recently submitting various deliverables and milestones:

- D7.12 '[System performance, monitoring and impact assessment r.2.0](#)'
- D6.1 '[Freshwater and iceberg flux impacts with BISICLES-NEMO](#)'
- MS12 '[The results of deliverables D2.1 and D4.1 are added to BISICLES- NEMO](#)'
- D2.1 '[Modelling icebergs, bathymetry and sea ice interactions](#)'

The progress and results of OCEAN ICE are published in deliverables and milestone reports.

In order to keep up with the OCEAN ICE deliverables and milestones, visit our [website](#) and stay tuned on our social media channels.

Upcoming Events

Climate Coffee

We have an upcoming Climate Coffee in November and December, make sure you register for all of them through the link on [OCEAN ICE](#).

Climate Coffee with Linus Vogt on Increased future ocean heat uptake constrained by Antarctic sea ice extent

19 February 2026, 15:00 – 15:45 (CET)

19 February 2026 | 15:00 - 15:45 CET

Online

Linus Vogt

(NYU, Sorbonne, LOCEAN)

**Increased future ocean heat uptake
constrained by Antarctic sea ice extent**

Climate Coffee with Giulia Bonino on Mediterranean summer marine heatwaves triggered by weaker winds under subtropical ridges

26 March 2026, 15:00 – 15:45 (CET)

26 March 2026 | 10:00 - 10:45 CET

Online

Giulia Bonino

(Euro-Mediterranean Center on Climate Change)

**Mediterranean summer marine
heatwaves triggered by weaker winds
under subtropical ridges**

Climate Coffee with Jens Terhaar on Record sea surface temperature jump in 2023–2024 unlikely but not unexpected

23 April 2026, 10:00 – 10:45 (CET)

23 April 2026 | 10:00 - 10:45 CEST
Online

Jens Terhaar
(University Bern)

**Record sea surface temperature jump
in 2023–2024 unlikely but not
unexpected**

Danish Meteorological Institute

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the European Union

OCEAN ICE at Ocean Sciences Meeting

Members from OCEAN ICE will be presenting at the [Ocean Sciences Meeting in Glasgow, Scotland 2026](#). Please find the below talks during the meeting and look out for any future sessions/talks too:

David Chandler, Petra Langebroek, Heiko Goelzer, Michele Petrini and Morven Muilwijk.

Abstract ID: 2009920

Abstract Title: Global impacts of Greenland and Antarctic ice sheet freshwater fluxes in the Norwegian Earth System Model (NorESM)

Final Abstract Number: HE43A-09

Presentation Type: Oral

Session Number and Title: HE43A: Ice Sheet–Ocean Interactions: From Micro- to Climate-Scale II Oral

Session Date and Time: Thursday, 26 February 2026; 14:00 - 15:30 GMT

Presentation Time: 15:20 - 15:30 GMT

Location: SEC; Hall 3, Blue Horizon

Timothee Bourgeois, David Chandler, Michele Petrini, Elin Darelius, Petra Langebroek, Heiko Goelzer, and Jörg Schwinger.

Abstract ID: 2008310

Abstract Title: Committed Southern Ocean warming and implications for the Antarctic Ice Sheet following emission cessation

Presentation Type: Poster

Session Date and Time: Thursday, 26 February 2026; 16:00 - 18:00 GMT

Session Number and Title: HE44D: Variability, Circulation, and Ongoing Change in the Southern Ocean VI Poster

Location: SEC; Hall 4 (Poster Hall)

Zhetao Tan:

Changing Properties of South Atlantic Upper-Ocean Water Masses During the Past 45 Years' in session PS21A - Atlantic Ocean Connectivity Across Latitudes: Large-Scale Processes, Observations, Modeling, and Impacts, which are targeted to the OCEAN ICE topic.

Session Date and Time: Tuesday, 24 February 2026, 09:23 - 09:33

Location: Hall 1 (SEC)

Happening Soon

OCEAN ICE will be at these upcoming events. Will you also be there? Let us know!

- 22nd – 27th February 2026, [Ocean Sciences Meeting](#), Glasgow, Scotland
- 9th – 13th March 2026, [CMIP 2026 Meeting](#), Kyoto, Japan
- 17th – 19th August 2026, [FRISP 2026](#), Kristineberg, Sweden

Do you know of any exciting events that OCEAN ICE should be a part of? Shoot us a mail at oceanice.eu@gmail.com.

Are you following us on Social Media?

Stay up to date with OCEAN ICE on our following channels:

www.ocean-ice.eu

<https://www.linkedin.com/company/euoceanice/>

https://twitter.com/OCEANICE_EU

<https://fediscience.org/@OceanIceEU>

<https://www.facebook.com/OCEANICEEU/>

[OCEAN ICE \(@oceaniceeu.bsky.social\) — Bluesky](#)

Who is OCEAN ICE?

OCEAN ICE stands for Ocean-Cryosphere Exchanges in Antarctica: Impacts on Climate and the Earth System. OCEAN ICE is a Horizon Europe project, funded by the European Commission and UKRI. OCEAN ICE focus on understanding how the Antarctic ice sheet and the surrounding Southern Ocean influence our global climate and reduce the level of uncertainty around how much the Antarctic ice sheet will melt in the coming centuries. OCEAN ICE considers the critical role of feedbacks between ocean circulation, ice sheet change and tipping points and the global climate. [Find out more](#)

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